

Women Contribution in Trade: Evidence of Southern African Development Community

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

This paper entitled Women Contribution in Trade in the Southern African Development Community. We aim to evaluate the contribution of female in trade in SADC and to help nations in designing appropriate strategies and policies to sustain the objective of gender equality in the new trading system. The literature review shows the benefits in empowering women and their contribution into trade matters. The model used derived from type Cobb-Douglas function. Our model derived from the production function (Cobb-Douglas version) in Solow-Swan model with technological progress: progress: $y = AK^\alpha L^\beta$ With the log linearization of introduction of control variable our model becomes $y = f(K, L, X)$

$\ln \text{net}B_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{FDI}_{ij} + \beta_2 X_{ij} + \beta_3 M_{ij} + \beta_4 \text{Rev}_{ij} + \beta_5 \text{Lw}_{ij} + \beta_6 \text{Business}_{ij} + \beta_7 \text{Travel}_{ij} + \beta_8 \text{Life_Exp}_{ij} + \beta_9 \text{Infl}_{ij} + \varepsilon_{it}$. The results from the analysis demonstrate the importance and the significance of women's contribution in trade in SADC. More opportunities and privileges need to be given to female in workplaces and businesses for their empowerment

Keywords: NET BARTER TERM, WOMEN EMPOWERMENT, TRADE, SADC

I-Introduction

In a globalized world, the pressure generated by trade raises the cost of discrimination against women ([world bank 2020 \(1\)](#)). There is a dissymmetric in woman participation in growth domestic product share. For a diversity of reasons, inequalities exist between men and women throughout the Southern African Development Community (SADC) region. Women are the majority of the lower class of population in SADC. Many are the reasons such as: restrictive and discriminatory laws, limited access to things compare to men, high illiteracy rates, and control over productive resources, culture or other factors. The experience has shown that countries in which women are not allow to fully contribute in the economy are less competitive internationally compare to those with export industries that have high female employment rates ([World Bank, 2 \(2\)](#)). However, equal rights between men and women are preserved as an essential human right in the UN Charter, and many international conferences have been held to further that goal as example the 1995 Beijing Declaration and Platform for Action. Distinguished progress has been made

in key areas such as women's contribution in the labor force; women's education at the primary, secondary and university levels. We can see that there are signs of a narrowing of the wage gap between men and women in many countries especially in the industrialized economy. Among the forces of globalization, international trade is one of the most significant channels that may bring additional challenges and opportunities. Questions arise regarding how the costs and benefits of trade can be equally distributed by gender, and if trade principles and policies expand or reduce the existing gender inequalities and what are the contribution of women in trade expansion. There is therefore a need to evaluate the contribution of female in questions related to trade in SADC and to help nations in designing appropriate strategies and policies to sustain the objective of gender equality in the new trading system.

II-Literature review

According to the literature, there are four channels through which trade can impact female labor contribution. The identified channels are sectorial reallocation of labor, technological upgrading, increased rivalry, and changes in discriminatory behavior. The sectorial reallocation deals with difference across sectors and the rest explain the divergences across types of firms (Rocha and Winkler 2019 (3)). There are a lot of benefit in empowering women, in this research we will focus mostly on the benefits on economic empowerment of women which includes the ability to contribute equally in existing markets; the right of entry to and control over productive resources, the access to respectable work; and increased voice, agency and significant participation in economic decision-making at all levels. Women empowerment can reduce or close gender gap in line with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs): achieving gender equality (Goal5), realizing the gender equality, promoting full and productive employment and decent work for all (Goal8), ending poverty (Goal11), food security (Goal 2), ensuring health (Goal3) and on reducing inequalities (Goal10) (UN report, 2016). Cuberes and Teignier (2016 (4)) stated that the women and girl educational attainment is positively related to the effort to empower them and to more inclusive economic growth.

The education can up skill and re-skill over the life course particularly to keep pace with rapid technological and digital changes affecting employments as well as their income-generation opportunities and participation in the formal labor market. Compare to men, women are as good at doing business as men. Companies significantly benefit from increasing employment and leadership opportunities for women, which is shown to increase organizational effectiveness and growth. It is estimated that companies with three or more women in senior management functions score higher in all dimensions of organizational performance (McKinsey & Company, 2018 (5)). Women's economic empowerment is also responsible in boosting the productivity which leads to increases economic diversification and income equality and other positive development outcomes (IMF, 2018 (6)), with knowledge that growth does not automatically lead to a reduction in gender-based inequality (Cuberes and Teignier, 2016 (7)).

Despite their importance in the society, women in many cases are more likely to be unemployed than men, they are over-represented in informal and vulnerable employment (Hash, 2019) and remain less likely to participate in the labor market than men around the world (UN, 2018; ILO, 2018 (8)). They own less income compare to men (Grimshaw, 2015 (9); with disproportionate responsibility for unpaid care and domestic work (ILO, 2017 (10); OECD, 2014 (11)). Even though some efforts are significant to empower women, they are still less likely to have access to social protection (ILO, 2016 (12)), less likely than men to have access to financial institutions or have a bank account (Demirguc-Kunt, 2015 (13)), constrained from achieving the highest leadership positions (Cheryl, 2014 (14)), are less likely to be entrepreneurs and face more disadvantages starting businesses (Global Entrepreneurship Monitor, 2017 (15)).

The agriculture sector including forestry and fishing is globally composed of a third of women's employment (Economic and Social Council, 2018 (16)) and a significant share of women farmers don't have access, control over, and ownership over the land and other productive assets (FAO, 2015 (17)). They are more likely to carry the burden of energy poverty and experience the adverse effects of lack of safe, affordable, reliable, and clean energy and the environmental degradation and climate change have disproportionate impacts on women and children. On top of all, women's migration is more significant compare to men (Goff et al. 2016 (18); UN Department of Economic and Social Affairs, 2017 (19); López-Anuarbe, 2016 (20)).

III-Materials and methods

Our model derived from the production function (Cobb-Douglas version) in Solow-Swan model with technological progress:

$$y = AK^{\alpha}L^{\beta} \quad (1)$$

With the log linearization of introduction of control variable our model becomes

$$y = f(K, L, X) \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \ln \text{net}B_{ij} = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 FDI_{ij} + \beta_2 X_{ij} + \beta_3 M_{ij} + \beta_4 Rev_{ij} + \beta_5 Lw_{ij} + \beta_6 Business_{ij} + \beta_7 Travel_{ij} \\ & + \beta_8 Life_Exp_{ij} + \beta_9 Infl_{ij} + \varepsilon_{it} \end{aligned}$$

3.1. Variable Description

Net barter terms of trade index ($\ln \text{net}B_{ij}$): is calculated as the percentage ratio of the export unit value indexes to the import unit value indexes, measured relative to the base year 2000.

Foreign Direct Investment (FDI_{ij}): It refers to direct investment equity flows in the reporting economy. It is the sum of equity capital, reinvestment of earnings, and other capital.

Exports (X_{ij}): represent the value of all goods and other market services provided to the rest of the world.

Imports (M_{ij}): represent the value of all goods and other market services received from the rest of the world.

Revenue (Rev_{ij}): Are cash receipts from taxes, social contributions, and other revenues such as fines, fees, rent, and income from property or sales.

Labor force (Lw_{ij}): Labor force with intermediate education, female (% of female working-age population with intermediate education).

Business ($Business_{ij}$): Dummy Variable A woman can register a business in the same way as a man (1=yes; 0=no)

Travel ($Travel_{ij}$): Dummy Variable A woman can travel outside her home in the same way as a man (1=yes; 0=no)

Life expectancy ($Life_Exp_{ij}$): Life expectancy at birth indicates the number of years a newborn infant would live if prevailing patterns of mortality at the time of its birth were to stay the same throughout its life.

3.2. Results and explanation

Descriptive statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev	Min	Max
Lnetb	450	4.65031	0.2496893	3.791659	5.521753
Lnfdi	417	18.94542	1.840023	9.21034	23.02867
Lx	412	21.75401	1.433381	17.68594	25.56623
Lm	412	42.44163	22.7601	2.308278	117.1538
Rev	303	25.23804	10.56489	5.922756	52.78838
Llw	420	14.16917	1.693392	10.45878	16.48576
Busi	450	.7844444	.4116649	0	1
Travel	450	.9822222	.1322899	0	1
Bank	450	.7844444	.4116649	0	1
Life_Ex	450	59.68206	9.097101	44.595	80.2
Infl	448	124.7715	1315.237	-27.04865	26765.86

IV-Results

VARIABLES	OLS	OLS	OLS	FE	RE
	Lnetb	Lnetb	lnetb	Lnetb	lnetb
Lnfdi	-0.0287*** (0.00807)	0.0169 (0.0147)	-0.0322*** (0.00833)	-0.0288*** (0.00795)	-0.0287*** (0.00807)
Lx	0.218*** (0.0219)	0.176*** (0.0237)	0.218*** (0.0366)	0.275*** (0.0269)	0.218*** (0.0219)
M	-0.00514*** (0.00102)	-0.000489 (0.00125)	-0.00565*** (0.00118)	-0.00557*** (0.00102)	-0.00514*** (0.00102)
Rev	0.00641*** (0.00228)	-0.0136*** (0.00281)	0.0104*** (0.00240)	0.00769*** (0.00226)	0.00641*** (0.00228)
Llw	0.0584 (0.0363)	0.108*** (0.0187)	0.399** (0.157)	0.259*** (0.0756)	0.0584 (0.0363)
Business	0.141*** (0.0404)	0.180*** (0.0642)	0.217*** (0.0437)	0.189*** (0.0430)	0.141*** (0.0404)
Travel	0.311*** (0.118)	0.391 (0.238)	0.113 (0.125)	0.251** (0.116)	0.311*** (0.118)
life_ex	-0.000913 (0.00169)	-0.0154*** (0.00294)	0.000296 (0.00240)	0.000398 (0.00175)	-0.000913 (0.00169)
Infl	-0.000656** (0.000289)	0.000441 (0.000486)	-0.000847*** (0.000302)	-0.000622** (0.000283)	-0.000656** (0.000289)
Constant	1.568*** (0.406)	3.483*** (0.354)	6.438*** (2.146)	2.843*** (0.637)	1.568*** (0.406)
Time FE	NO	YES	YES		
Country FE	NO	NO	YES		
Observations	237	237	237	237	237
Number of id	13	13	13	13	13
R-squared				0.574	

Standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Hausman Test

Test: Ho: difference in coefficients not systematic

$$\text{Chi2 (9)} = (\mathbf{b}-\mathbf{B})'[(\mathbf{V}_b-\mathbf{V}_B)^{-1}](\mathbf{b}-\mathbf{B}) = 21.04$$

Prob>chi2 = 0.0125 ($\mathbf{V}_b-\mathbf{V}_B$ is not positive definite)

The probability is less than 5%, we reject the null hypothesis meaning that the Fixed Effect Model is appropriate.

The table above presents different but quite similar results from different methods of estimation we conducted. The first three are gotten with the Ordinary Least square method with no control of Time and Country Specifics effect in the column 1, the only the control of Time specific effect in the column 2 and with the control of both Time and Country Specifics effect in the column 3. The column 4 is the Fixed Effect model and the column 5 is the Random Effect model. The Hausman test performed suggests the Fixed Effect Model is appropriate for our regression.

The coefficient of the Foreign Direct investment is statistically and highly significant at 1% level. It is negatively related to the Net Barter Term meaning, holding all factors constant, 1% decline in the FDI will increase the Net Barter Term by about 0.03%. This can be explained by the mismanagement, the level of corruption and the areas where the FDI are directed.

The export is positively related to the Net Barter Term. The coefficient is statistically and highly significant at 1% level. *Ceteris paribus*, 1% increase in the export will also increase the Net Barter Term by about 0.27%. This confirms the economic thoughts and formulas.

The coefficient is statistically and highly significant at 1% level. It is negatively related to the Net Barter Term. Holding all the factors constant, 1% increase in the import will decrease the Net Barter Term by about 0.005%. This confirms the economic thoughts and formulas.

The coefficient of revenue stands for cash receipts from taxes, social contributions, and other revenues such as fines, fees, rent, and income from property or sales is highly significant and positively related to the Net Barter Term. 1% change in the revenue will lead to 0.007% change in the Net Barter Term in the same direction, holding everything constant.

Labor force with intermediate education, female used in the research is the proxy of female labor force participation in the GDP. The coefficient of the female labor force is highly significant at 1% level of significance and positively related to the Net Barter Term. A percentage increase in the female labor force will increase the Net Barter Term by about 0.25%, holding constant all the factors. This shows the importance and the significance of female labor force in the trade activities.

The dummy variable used to capture how ease is for a woman can register a business in the same way as a man is significant and positively associated to the Net Barter Term. If the SADC members individually ameliorate by a percentage the environment of doing businesses for female, the Net Barter Term will also increase by about 0.2%, *ceteris paribus*.

The dummy variable used to capture how ease is for a woman can travel outside her home in the same way as a man is significant and positively associated to the Net Barter Term. If the SADC members individually give more opportunities to women to travel often for businesses purposes, it will ameliorate the Net Barter Term *ceteris paribus*.

Conclusion

In our research entitled Women Contribution in Trade: Evidence of Southern African Development Community, we aim to evaluate the contribution of female in questions related to trade in SADC and to help nations in designing appropriate strategies and policies to sustain the objective of gender equality in the new trading system. The literature review shows that there are a lot of benefits in empowering women and they contribute equally in existing markets. The results from the analysis demonstrate the importance and the significance of women's contribution in trade in SADC. More opportunities and privileges need to be given to female in workplaces and businesses for their empowerment. Though more entrepreneurs are men, women are known to negotiate contracts efficiently better than men (Robyn Parets, 2019).

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